

Let the loss function be $L = L(C)$, and in turn $C = AB$. So $C_{ij} = \sum_k A_{ik} B_{kj}$. Then we compute the gradient, $\frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{ij}} = \sum_{kl} \frac{\partial L}{\partial C_{kl}} \frac{\partial C_{kl}}{\partial A_{ij}} = \sum_{kl} \frac{\partial L}{\partial C_{kl}} \delta_{ki} B_{jl} = \sum_l \frac{\partial L}{\partial C_{il}} B_{jl} = (\frac{\partial L}{\partial C} B^T)_{ij}$. So $A_{grad} = C_{grad} B^T$. Similar for other cases.